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THE INFLUENCE OF BRAND IMAGE AND BRAND TRUST ON LOYALTY MEDIATED BY CONSUMER SATISFACTION ON PURCHASES OF MR.DIY PRODUCTS IN SELONG CITY

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of brand image and brand trust on consumer loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction with purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City. The population in this study are consumers who have shopped at MR.DIY in Selong City using a sample of $10 \times 10 = 100$ respondents. The research method used in this research is quantitative. This research is associative, using SEM-PLS with SmartPLS 0.4. The research results show (1) Brand Image does not have a positive and significant influence on consumer loyalty, (2) Brand Image has a positive and insignificant influence on consumer satisfaction, (3) Brand Trust has a positive and significant influence on consumer loyalty, (4) Brand Trust has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction, (5) Consumer Loyalty has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction, (6) Brand Image has a positive and insignificant influence on consumer loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction, (7) Brand Trust has a positive and significant influence on consumer loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction with product purchases MR.DIY in Selong City.

Key Words: Brand Image, Brand Trust, Loyalty, and Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Background

Along with the development of the times and digital technology in the industry 4.0 era, competition in the business world has become very rapid. This is due to the many forms of business that have main objectives, namely technical and economic objectives. The technical goal is how the company produces products that suit consumer tastes, while the economic goal is to generate maximum profits.

Economic developments have had a significant impact on business players globally, including Indonesia. Indonesia as a developing country has many industrial sectors that can be developed, one of which is the retail industry. The retail industry is a business that is a large supply chain for society because the large number of goods provided can fulfill some of society's needs. Currently, the retail industry has experienced development, which was initially traditional and has now become modern. The performance of the retail sector contributes 53.56% of gross domestic product (GDP) in the main household sector (source. DDTC News 2022). The following is retail business sales data in Indonesia in July 2023-2024:

Figure 1.1 Total Retail Business Sales in Indonesia

Source: Bank Indonesia (2024)

Based on statistical data for 2023-2024 according to Bank Indonesia above, retail sales in Indonesia increased by 5.8% on an

annual basis in August 2024, an increase from an increase of 4.5% in the previous July. This marks consumer satisfaction from increasing retail sales for 4 consecutive months and the fastest pace since March, with sales of 9.3%. However, in April 2024 there was a decrease of (-2.7%) due to cultural & recreational factors. For September, sales are estimated to increase by 4.7% from the previous month. On a monthly basis, retail sales rose 1.7% in August 2024, which bounced back from a 7.2% decline in May which was the sharpest decline in a year.

Consumer loyalty is a long-term commitment to a brand and persists deeply to re-subscribe in order to consistently re-purchase products/services in the future, even though situational influences and marketing efforts have the potential to cause changes in behavior. Consumers are willing to pay more for a product with a certain brand if the product is attached to a brand that guarantees consistency in quality and believed value. Consumer loyalty is influenced by satisfaction, product quality and service experience. Customer loyalty is not formed in a short time but rather through the results of consumer experiences from consistent purchases over time.

MR.DIY is a retail company originating from Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. He opened his first shop on Jalan Tuanku Abdul Rahman Kuala Lumpur in July 2005. This company has expanded its presence in various Asian countries such as Indonesia, Thailand, the Philippines, Singapore, Brunei, Cambodia, Turkey, India and Vietnam. MR.DIY is an international brand that has a good brand image and trust in the eyes of consumers. The MR.DIY brand is designed and produced to help with daily needs. Each product is designed to maintain its quality to gain brand trust from consumers. All MR.DIY stores are managed directly by the company and collaborate with large resellers, mall owners and other property owners.

MR.DIY (Mister Do It Yourself) which means "do it yourself". This word or activity has long been used in the United States. Basically it is indicated for activities that lead to building, assembling, making your own activities without the help of experts (www.mr.diy.com).

Table 1.1 MR.DIY Group Financial Report (USD)

Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total income	2,28	2,56 + 12,47%	3,37 +31,81%	3,99 +18,15%	4,36 +9,37%
Profit bruto/gross profit	628,50	673,48	839,72	966,37	1,14
Pretax Income	436,03	455,76	584,29	637,34	749,55
Net income	317,57 +3,00%	337,16 +6,17%	431,83 +28,08%	472,95 +9,52%	560,67 +18,55%

Source : www.mr.diy.com (2024)

The Management Discussion & Analysis report stated that MR.DIY Group (M) Berhad 2024 was named the favorite retail company in Southeast Asia. MR.DIY won the WBA (World Branding Award) award in the Regional Top Home Improvement Retail Brand category. This award is given by the WBF (World Branding Forum) which is a global non-profit organization dedicated to advancing branding standards for the good of the branding community and consumers. MR.DIY has successfully worked in the fields of branding, design, marketing, advertising and consumer relations in the business world. This company was present for the first time in Indonesia in September 2017 and collaborates under the auspices of Aeon, ITC Group, Pakuwon, Lippo Group, Ramayana, and Citymall. MR.DIY comes with a supermarket concept that offers more

than 18,000 selected products in categories such as tools, household furniture, electricity, car accessories, stationery, sports equipment, toys, gifts, computer and cellphone accessories, jewelry and cosmetics (www.mrdiy.com)

Based on the background description above, researchers are interested in researching "The Influence of Brand Image and Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty Mediated by Mr.Diy Product Satisfaction in Selong City".

Research Problems

To find out the challenges and threats faced by the company so that it can maintain its best condition in the eyes of consumers. Apart from that, it is necessary to consider consumer satisfaction because that is one of the things that can influence whether consumers are loyal or not when shopping. On the other hand, consumers also consider the company's brand image and brand trust.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is the result of the difference between expectations and performance perceived by consumers. Satisfaction is an assessment of the uniqueness or features of a product or service that provides a level of customer satisfaction by fulfilling consumer needs. The theory of consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction (The Expectancy Disconfirmation Model) explains that the impact of comparing consumer expectations before purchasing with what consumers actually get from the product purchased. Indicators of consumer satisfaction according to (Rondonuwu & Komalig) in (Junaedi, 2021:12) are the fulfillment of consumer expectations, service quality, location.

Consumer Loyalty

According to Oliver (2022:9) Consumer loyalty is a consumer's deep commitment to be able to buy products consistently in the future even though the influence of conditions and marketing efforts has the potential to cause changes in behavior. Indicators of Consumer Loyalty according to Kotler & Keller (2021, Vol.1 No.5 p. 377) are divided into 3, namely Repeat Purchase (loyalty to repurchase), Retention (endurance), and Referrals (recommendations).

Brand Image

According to Sari Dewi et.al. (2020, pp. 256-267), brand image is the way consumers view a brand as an image of what is in the consumer's thoughts or minds regarding a brand. The brand image must convey the benefits and unique positioning of the product, even when competing offers must look the same, buyers must feel the difference based on brand image differentiation. Brand Image Indicators according to Papatungan (2023) in Anngelita et.al (2024, p.840) Brand Image has 3 indicators used including brand strength (Strength Of Brand Association), brand uniqueness (Uniqueness Of Brand Association), and brand excellence (Favorability Of Brand Association).

Brand Trust

In (Armanto, Islamiah and Gunarto, 2022:59) states that Brand Trust is the ability of a brand to be trusted which originates from the consumer's belief that the product brand is able to fulfill the value promised by the producer and good brand trust which is realized by the consumer's belief that the brand can prioritize consumer needs. Brand trust is the ability to make oneself aware of relationships with partners that are based on faith. According to Pandingan & Ali (2021) in (Hayati, 2022 Vol.3 No.3) Brand Trust has 2 dimensions, namely the Dimension of Viability (viability dimension) and the Dimension of Intentionality (intentionality dimension).

Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is associative with a quantitative approach. This research includes causal associative research. This research was conducted in Selong City, East Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara. The time of this research is from September 2024 to December 2024. The population in this research is all consumers who have shopped at MR.DIY Selong City. The data collection method used was a survey sample. The technique used in sampling is a non-probability sampling technique with purposive sampling technique. The data collection techniques used were questionnaires and interviews using Google forms. The data analysis used was Partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4.0 software. The results of data analysis tested the measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that those interested in purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City, based on the gender of the respondents, were mostly men with a total of 53 respondents. Meanwhile, the characteristics of the respondents were based on the majority aged 17-25 years with a total of 87 people. And the characteristics of respondents based on their last education were dominated by high school graduates, 61 people. And the characteristics of respondents based on work were 64 people not working (college students/housewives). And based on income, more consumers

have income < Rp. 1,500,000, namely 70 people. And the characteristics of respondents are based on their purchases 38 times. This means that consumers often purchase MR.DIY products more than 7 times, 38. This reflects the level of satisfaction, loyalty and trust in the MR.DIY brand image in Selong City.

Test Outer Model

1. Convergent validity test

Convergent validity testing in Partial Least Squares (PLS) using reflective indicators is evaluated based on the loading factor (correlation between item/component scores and construct scores) of the indicators that measure the construct. The higher the factor loading value, the more significant the loading influence is in the interpretation of the factor matrix. The rule of thumb commonly used to measure convergent validity is outer loading > 0.7. However, a reflective manifest variable is considered to meet convergent validity if it has outer loading, average extracted (AVE), and communalty values above 0.5 (Hair et al., 2011).

Table 4.6 Loading Factor Value for Each Indicator on the Variable

No.	Variabel	Items	Outer Loading	Information
1.	Brand Image	X1.1	0.838	Valid
		X1.2	0.759	Valid
		X1.3	0.866	Valid
		X1.4	0.849	Valid
		X1.5	0.837	Valid
		X1.6	0.841	Valid
2.	Brand Trust	X2.1	0.886	Valid
		X2.2	0.849	Valid
		X2.3	0.843	Valid
		X2.4	0.903	Valid
		X2.5	0.825	Valid
		X2.6	0.893	Valid
		X2.7	0.803	Valid
		X2.8	0.878	Valid
3.	Customer Loyalty	Y.1	0.856	Valid
		Y.2	0.847	Valid
		Y.3	0.877	Valid
		Y.4	0.718	Valid
		Y.5	0.883	Valid
		Y.6	0.767	Valid
4.	Consumer Satisfaction	Z.1	0.923	Valid
		Z.2	0.912	Valid
		Z.3	0.803	Valid

Source: Primary Data Processed 2025

Outer factor is a coefficient that explains the level of relationship between the indicator and the latent variable. In general, the higher the outer factor value, the better the relationship or it can be said to be valid. The outer factor is said to be good if the value is above 0.70. Based on table 4.6, the outer factor value of all indicators for the latent variable is above 0.07. This shows that all indicators in this research have a valid relationship with the latent variable.

Table 4.7 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	AVE Value	AVE Value Limit	Decision
Brand Image (X1)	0,693	0,5	Fulfilled
Brand Trust (X2)	0,741	0,5	Fulfilled

Customer Loyalty	0,684	0,5	Fulfilled
Consumer Satisfaction	0,776	0,5	Fulfilled

Source: SmartPLS 2025 Output Results

Table 4.7 above shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for Brand Image, Brand Trust, Loyalty and Consumer Satisfaction has produced an AVE value greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the indicators used in this research are declared valid, because they meet the requirements for Convergent Validity.

2. Discriminant Validity Test

In this research, the Discriminant Validity of the measurement model with reflected indicators can be assessed based on Cross Loading measurements with the construct. If the value of the cross loading on each indicator has a value greater than the value of the cross loading on other latent variables with a value > 0.5 then it can be said to be valid (Supriyanto & Maharani, 2013).

Table 4.8 Results of Cross Loading Values

	Brand Image	Brand Trust	Loyalty	Satisfaction
X1.1	0.838	0.631	0.449	0.597
X1.2	0.759	0.427	0.428	0.503
X1.3	0.866	0.630	0.537	0.555
X1.4	0.849	0.639	0.567	0.548
X1.5	0.837	0.590	0.466	0.581
X1.6	0.841	0.623	0.533	0.578
X2.1	0.650	0.886	0.721	0.744
X2.2	0.571	0.849	0.686	0.671
X2.3	0.615	0.843	0.616	0.773
X2.4	0.678	0.903	0.698	0.695
X2.5	0.551	0.825	0.538	0.613
X2.6	0.636	0.893	0.719	0.725
X2.7	0.564	0.803	0.628	0.652
X2.8	0.632	0.878	0.736	0.684
Y.1	0.477	0.665	0.856	0.587
Y.2	0.487	0.602	0.847	0.600
Y.3	0.488	0.702	0.877	0.749
Y.4	0.359	0.432	0.718	0.446
Y.5	0.552	0.695	0.883	0.721
Y.6	0.567	0.701	0.767	0.725
Z.1	0.630	0.781	0.710	0.923
Z.2	0.568	0.714	0.701	0.912
Z.3	0.582	0.636	0.669	0.803

Source: SmartPLS 2025 Output Results

3. Reliability Test

Calculation of the Composite Reliability value is done by looking at the Composite Reliability value of the indicators that measure the value of the variable, and the indicator will have a good composite reliability value if the value is > 0.7 or it can be concluded that the variable has fulfilled the aspects and the indicators are consistent or reliable in presenting the latent variable.

Table 4.9 Composite Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Information
Brand image	0.911	0.913	0.931	Reliabel
Brand trust	0.950	0.952	0.958	Reliabel
Loyalty	0.907	0.918	0.928	Reliabel
Satisfaction	0.853	0.859	0.912	Reliabel

Source: Primary Data Processed 2025

Test the Inner Model

1. R-Square

According to Hair et al., (2017), 0.25 indicates low influence, 0.5 indicates medium influence, and 0.7 indicates high influence. But the higher the R-Square value, the greater the variable.

Table 4.10 R-Square Value Results

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted	Information
Customer Loyalty (Y)	0.679	0.669	Tall
Customer Satisfaction (Z)	0.674	0.667	Satisfied

Source: Primary data processed in 2025

2. Q-Square

The assessment of goodness of fit is known from the q-square value. The q-square value has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination (r-square) in regression analysis. It is said that the higher the q-square value, the better or better the model can be said to fit the data. The results of the Q-square calculation in this research are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Q-Square} &= 1-(1-R^2_1) \times (1-R^2_2) \\
 &= 1-(1-0.679) \times (1-0.674) \\
 &= 1-(0.321) \times (0.326) \\
 &= 0.89
 \end{aligned}$$

3. Hypothesis Testing

T-statistics and p-values are used in hypothesis testing to ensure whether a hypothesis is accepted or rejected. The hypothesis was tested using the SmartPLS.04 tool using a bootstrapping strategy. Where this relationship will be significant if the P-value is smaller than the alpha value (P-value ≤ α). In this research, the alpha (α) value is 0.05 or 5%.

Table 4.11 Part Coefficient or Direct Effect Test Results

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Information
X1 -> Y	-0.001	0.036	0.113	0.009	0.993	Not Significant
X1 -> Z	0.197	0.256	0.161	1.221	0.222	Not Significant
X2 -> Y	0.413	0.387	0.129	3.188	0.001	Significant
X2 -> Z	0.669	0.606	0.157	4.249	0.000	Significant
Z -> Y	0.454	0.446	0.125	3.623	0.000	Significant

Source: SmartPLS Output Results (2025)

The direct impact data from the path coefficient which shows the influence of Brand Image on consumer loyalty through consumer satisfaction is presented in table 4.11. This influence is classified as insignificant because the t-statistic value is < 1.96 and P-value > 0.05. Apart from that, the influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty through Consumer Satisfaction is classified as significant because the t-statistic value exceeds 1.96 and the p-value is below 0.05. Furthermore, the influence of consumer satisfaction on consumer loyalty is known to have a t-statistic value exceeding 1.96 and a p-value of less than 0.05.

Table 4.12 Direct Effect Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Construct	Information
1	The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty	Rejected
2	The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction	Rejected
3	The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty	Accepted
4	The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Satisfaction	Accepted
5	The Influence of Consumer Satisfaction on Consumer Loyalty	Accepted

Source: Processed data (2025)

4. Mediation Test

The mediation test is used to test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable which is mediated by the intervening variable.

Table 4.13 Results of Specific Indirect Effects or Indirect Effects

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Information
X1 -> Z -> Y	0.089	0.112	0.075	1.186	0.236	Not Significant
X2 -> Z -> Y	0.304	0.274	0.114	2.673	0.008	Significant

Source: SmartPLS 4.0 Output Results (2025)

Based on the findings of certain indirect influences in table 4.13, it can be seen that the influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty through the mediation of Consumer Satisfaction was found to be insignificant. This happens because the t-statistic value is < 1.96 and the p-value is > 0.05. Meanwhile, the influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty through the mediation of Consumer Satisfaction has proven to be significant, this is shown by the t-statistic value > 1.96 and p-value < 0.05.

Table 4.14 Results of Specific Indirect Effects or Indirect Effects

Hypothesis	Construct	Information
6	The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty Mediated by Consumer Satisfaction	Rejected
7	The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty Mediated by Consumer Satisfaction	Accepted

Source: Primary data processing results (2025)

5. Goodness Of fit results

This test was carried out to assess the degree of conformity between the model and the data used in the research. This research uses the Fit SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square) model with a benchmark of <0.08 for good SRMR results.

Table 4.15. SRMR value

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.067	0.067

Source: SmartPLS Output Results (2025)

Table 4.14 shows that the achieved SRMR value of 0.67 is below the threshold of 0.08. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model used is in accordance with the empirical data in this research.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty
It was found that there was no positive and significant effect. The p-value of 0.993 shows the significance of the p-value > 0.05 and the t-statistic value of 0.009 is much smaller than 1.96. This could possibly happen because MR.DIY products are not products that require consideration of Brand Image when choosing or buying

2. The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction
It was found that there was a positive and insignificant effect. The results of this research show that to gain a brand image from consumers, companies must pay attention to several factors that can influence consumer satisfaction. One of the factors that can influence consumer satisfaction is consumer perception of a brand. A strong brand image has a big influence on consumer satisfaction. A positive brand image creates high expectations in the minds of consumers. If the product or repeatedly. However, in repeated purchases (habitual buying) the need to choose a brand is often ignored because purchases are made based on needs, not desires.

service matches the expected image, consumer satisfaction will increase.

3. The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty

The results of the analysis state that there is a positive and significant influence. This is proven by the path coefficient value of 0.413, indicating a positive relationship, the p-value of 0.001 indicating the significance of this influence, the p-value < 0.05 and the t-statistic value of 3.188 > 1.96. These results show that the third hypothesis (H3), namely "The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty in Purchasing MR.DIY Products in Selong City" is acceptable and in accordance with the results of the research conducted.

4. The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

The results of data analysis state that brand trust has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction. This states that consumers have confidence in MR.DIY products so they continue to make purchases. Brand trust plays an important role in building long-term relationships between brands and consumers so that consumers feel satisfaction with the product. The factor that builds brand trust in consumer satisfaction is the reliability of a brand. Consumers feel satisfied if the brand consistently meets their expectations in terms of product quality, service or value provided, thereby increasing their sense of trust and providing satisfaction to consumers.

5. The Influence of Consumer Satisfaction on Loyalty

Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that there was a significant and positive relationship between consumer satisfaction and consumer loyalty. This is proven by the path coefficient value of 0.454, which shows that there is a positive relationship between loyalty and consumer satisfaction. Apart from that, the p-value of 0.000 shows the significance of this influence. The p-value is < 0.05 and the t-statistic value is 3.623 > 1.96. With consumer satisfaction, it can be seen from how satisfied consumers feel with the performance provided by MR.DIY products to meet consumer expectations so that consumers feel satisfied and will create consumer loyalty to the brand.

6. The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty Through Satisfaction

Based on the results of research that has been conducted, Brand Image has an insignificant positive influence on Consumer Loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction. The results of this research show that Brand Image can mediate consumer satisfaction on consumer loyalty. Companies must focus on improving brand image through quality, profit, trusted, services, costs, and brand or image itself, which are factors that form brand image and have a deep relationship so that consumers are satisfied with a product, thereby creating sustainable customer loyalty.

7. The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Loyalty Through Satisfaction

Based on the results of research that has been conducted, Brand Trust has a significant and positive influence on Consumer Loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction. This is proven by the path coefficient value of 0.089, indicating a positive relationship between Brand Trust and Loyalty through Consumer Satisfaction. Apart from

that, the p-value of 0.008 shows the significance of this influence. The p-value is < 0.05 and the t-statistic value is 2.673 > 1.96. So it can be concluded that consumer satisfaction plays a full mediating role.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and data analysis regarding the influence of brand image and brand trust on consumer loyalty which is mediated by consumer satisfaction when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1 Brand image does not have a positive and significant influence on consumer loyalty when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City.
- 2 Brand image has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer satisfaction when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City
- 3 Brand Trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City
- 4 Brand Trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City
- 5 Consumer loyalty has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction when purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City
- 6 Brand image has a positive and insignificant effect on consumer loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction with purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City
- 7 Brand trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty which is mediated by satisfaction with purchasing MR.DIY products in Selong City

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